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ENVIRONMENTAL SANITATION STUDY ON SUKENA VILLAGE, DISTRICT - NASHIK, MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract:

The aim of this study was to assess the environmental sanitation condition with regards to water, wastewater, solid waste management and hygiene of households of Sukeena village, District - Nashik, Maharashtra. Generally the households had good domestic environmental sanitation conditions but it also emerged that the households were deprived from full range of access to the most essential environmental sanitation services. The poor sanitation and lack of pure drinking water produced lots of problems over Sukeena village & increase in number of water borne diseases. The disposal and management of solid, liquid and grey water waste should be done properly so as to keep away breeding mosquitoes and house flies from the Sukeena village.

In this study, the physicochemical parameters such as pH, TDS, DO, BOD, Total Alkalinity, Total Hardness, Fluorides, Chloride, Nitrates, Iron etc. were analyzed to know the present status of the water quality during pre-monsoon & post-monsoon of 2013-14. Also contaminated water tested for various (pH, Total solids, BOD, COD, Salinity, Calcium, Magnesium, Sulphate, Nitrites, Total Organic Carbon, Surfactants, E. coli) parameters is collected from drainage line and some of the water samples affecting pesticides concentration like Atrazine, Aldrin; Dieldrin; 2, 4 - D; p, p DDT; o, p DDT; p, p DDE; o, p DDE; p, p DDD; o, p DDD; α Endosulfan; β Endosulfan; γ HCH (Lindane) in Sukeena village.

Pollution of soil was checked by testing various (pH, Bulk Density, Porosity, Water Holding Capacity, Organic Matter, Total Nitrogen, Available Phosphorus, Available Potassium, Cation Exchange Capacity, Available Boron, Nitrite and Acidity as CaCO_3) parameters with addition of solid waste management study, the construction details and design of the drainage chamber, composting pits, design of sanitary block should be analyzed.

Keywords: Environmental sanitation, Domestic water, Waste water, Solid waste, Physico-chemical parameters, Graph Analysis, Sukeena village.

I. INTRODUCTION

Environmental sanitation is nothing but the sanitation system affected on the human lives, as it is a major public health issue in India. Most of the cities and towns in India are characterized by over-crowding, congestion, inadequate water supply and inadequate facilities of disposal of human excreta, wastewater and solid wastes. The environmental sanitation still remains an ignored issue mainly in rural areas of India. The quality of water depends upon various chemical constituents and their concentration generated by fertilizers, industrial wastes, garbage or domestic wastes. The economic impacts of inadequate sanitation into the following categories: 1. Health-related impacts: Pre-mature deaths, costs of treating diseases; productive time lost due to people falling ill, and time lost by caregivers who look after them. 2. Domestic water-related impacts: Household treatment of water; use of bottled water; a portion of costs of obtaining piped water; and time costs of fetching cleaner water from a distance. 3. Access time impacts: Cost of additional time spent for accessing shared toilets or open defecation sites; absence of children (mainly girls) from school and women from their workplaces.

In the present study, Environmental Sanitation Study on Sukena village in Nasik district (Maharashtra). In this, the Gondegaon well water, tap water, contaminated water and contaminated soil and the water affected by pesticides, collected from the Gondegaon well and Bhandare's well (farmer) has been collected and the testing is to be done in the laboratory and gone through the linear regression analysis. The main problems occurred in environmental sanitation are the quality of water supplied to the village for the utilization of water in domestic purposes and other resources and the proper disposed off of human excreta. Many villagers are suffering from various water borne disease and diseases due to excretion of house flies etc.

Many researchers have attempted their research on different physico-chemical parameters of the water samples collected from various regions and conclusions regarding the safe secure, healthy water and environmental sanitation facilities.

II. METHODS AND MATERIALS

Village survey is done through all over the area so as to know the village population, supply of water to the villagers through Gondegaon well and Ban Ganga River, the disposal of waste water coming out from the households and sanitary blocks should be done properly and separately, with the help of Gram-Panchayat and PHC (Public Health Center), all the data's of all the data's of Sukena village and the water borne diseases affecting on the villagers. The village is having population of about 11610. The water samples are collected from the tap water (pre-monsoon and post-monsoon) in 2013-14, which is inter linked to the Godavari river to main water tank of Sukena Village; the Gondegaon well water, to check the quality of water, contaminated soil and grey water has been collected and testing is to be done in the laboratory to get the permissible values of the selective parameters. The experimentally calculated values are compared with the standard values of the water, grey water and soil by graphical means.

The occurrence of the ion and impurities in the water is mainly depends upon the improper collection and storage of water, improper handling of water carrying materials, improper hygienic condition, improper sanitation facilities, open disposal of waste etc.

Table 1: Latitude and Longitude of Study area

Village Name	Latitude	Longitude
Sukena (Kasbe Sukena)	20° 4' 60N	74° 1' 0E

The parameters for the drinking water analysis are: pH, Temperature, Alkalinity, Turbidity, Total Dissolved Solids, Dissolved Oxygen, Total Hardness, BOD, Fluorides, Chlorides, Nitrates and Iron. The parameters for the contaminated water analysis are: pH, Total solids, BOD, COD, Salinity, Calcium, Magnesium, Sulphates, Nitrites, Total Organic Carbon, Surfactant and E. coli and the parameters for the contaminated soil analysis are: pH, Bulk Density, Porosity, Water Holding Capacity, Organic Carbon, Total Nitrogen, Available Potassium, Available Phosphorus, Available Boron, Cation Exchange Capacity, Nitrites, Acidity.

The parameters for the water affected by the pesticides concentration, collected from the Gondegaon well and Bhandare well are: atrazine, aldrin, dieldrin, 2,4 - D; p, p DDT; o, p DDT; p, p DDE; o, p DDE; p, p DDD; o, p DDD; α Endosulfan, β Endosulfan, γ HCH (Lindane) respectively so as to check the concentration of pesticides present in the well water, whether it is harmful for the soil quality and water quality connected to the agriculture field.

The design and construction of drainage chamber is to be carried out with the help of Gram Panchayat and the accurate line out has been planned and the work is going on. The waste coming out from the house hold kitchens, basins, toilets etc. are being mixed, that should be segregated properly so that it can be easily disposed off. Next to that, the construction of manure pit (composting) with the detailed costing including number of bricks, material required. The contaminated soil and the contaminated water adversely affected due the close connections of main water pipe line and newly constructed drainage pipe line in one place. The calculation of per family solid waste disposed of by surveying in Sukena village and the costing for constructing a single toilet for the single family of the Sukena village. Posting the banners are also being designed to give message to the villagers about the hygienic health, proper utilization of sanitation facilities, to improve the lives of human beings in the Sukena Village. And while going through the survey, the major thing I have observed while constructing the drainage chamber, is that, the water pipeline allotted to the villagers for the utilization of domestic purpose are in the same place and parallel to the drainage pipeline. The main water pipelines should be located above the main drainage pipelines so as to avoid the mixing of waste water with the main drinking water.

The solid waste are of mainly various types, such as paper, plastic bags, bottles, vegetables wastes, ashes, fruit pulp and residue, egg pulp etc. from the domestic areas, streets whereas the plastic bags, polythene wrap over the medicines, bottles, syringe, saline bottles, cotton balls, etc from the health care centre situated in the Sukena village. By approximate calculation for the solid waste disposed off per family in the Sukena village is $0.1 \times 11610 = 1161 \text{ kg/day/capita} = 1.161 \text{ tonne (approx.1-2 kg/day/capita)}$. I am analyzing the solid waste collection of 14 days i.e. two weeks from one family. After analysis, the total solid waste collected is to be composting into the pit is 16.254 tonne and accordingly, the size of the composting pit will be 1 to 1.5 m long, 1 to 1.5 m wide and 1 m deep respectively.

The quantity of the solid waste coming out from single house is as follows:-

Glass – 15 to 20 % (12.93%);

Paper – 30 to 35 % (25.86%);

Metal – 9 to 10 % (7.758%);

Plastic – 10 to 15 % (8.625%);
Vegetable waste – 30 to 35 % (25.862%);
Dust, Cinders, Miscellaneous – 22 to 25% (18.965%);
Total waste – 116% (100%)

Figure 1: Pie Chart of the Waste

Most probably, the wastes are coming out from the residential, commercial, institutional and health centers. In this, the hazardous waste will be 1%, cotton or cloths will be 0.6%, plastics will be 20% glass will be 15%, paper will be 10% and others 0.4%.

Compost is important because it:-

- Contains main plant nutrients i.e. Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P), Potassium (K)
- Improves the organic matter in the soil by providing humus
- Help the soil to hold both water and air for plants.

Appropriate and safe excreta management is essential for the protection of human and environmental health, and also offers important social benefits to communities. Some of these benefits included in the elements described here under:-

1. **Human Health:** The impact of lack of basic sanitation is seen primarily in the area of health. Links between sanitation and health have long been established; health benefits of sanitation can be seen in the reduction of diseases in communities where sanitation facilities are present.

2. **Environmental Health:** The release of untreated excreta into the environment is a significant factor in the pollution and degradation of both water and soil quality. The effects of this can be seen in developing countries as most of the generated raw wastewater is discharged into surface water bodies.

3. **Poverty and Economy:** Sanitation related diseases exert a significant toll on the lives of people globally, it thus stands to reason that sanitation and related interventions will lead to an improvement in health, consequently productivity and ultimately poverty reduction. In addition to these positive effects of improved

sanitation on individual livelihood, there are indirect potential (communal and national) economic benefits as well.

4. Convenience, Privacy and Safety: Beyond health, access to toilets, enhances privacy, dignity and safety particularly for women.

5. Justice and equity: Equity and justice are fundamental principles underlining a sustainable society and development. It basically recognizes the right to water and sanitation as a human right, which when lacking negatively affects life, and as such is a vital component of the right to life, health, housing and education among other rights.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1: Experimentally Calculated values for post monsoon Nov - 2013 of Water Quality Parameters

Sr. no.	Characteristic	Experimentally calculated values	
		Tap water	Ghonde Gaon well water
1	pH	6.5	6.3
2	Temperature	25	25
3	Alkalinity	525	500
4	Hardness (mg/L)	570	375
5	Turbidity (NTU)	5	5
6	Total dissolved solids	950	900
7	BOD	3.5	3.2
8	DO (mg/L) (max.)	4.5	3.9
9	Fluorides (mg/L) (max.)	1.0	0.5
10	Chlorides (mg/L) (max.)	420	300
11	Nitrates (mg/L) (max.)	45	10
12	Iron (mg/L) (max.)	0.1	0.3

Figure 2: Graph Analysis on the Post monsoon (Nov 2013) Water Quality Parameters

The following parameters calculated from the experimental work are of post monsoon

Nov – 2013 of Sukena village are explained as follows:-

Temperature: In the present study, the temperature is 25°C.

pH: In the present study, pH is 6.5 for tap water and 6.3 for Gondegaon well water sample. The tolerance pH limit is 6.5 – 8.5.

TDS: In the present study, total dissolved solids value is 950 for the tap water and 900 for the Gondegaon well water sample. According to Indian Standards, TDS value should be less than 500 mg/L for drinking water.

D.O.: In the present study, the dissolved oxygen is 4.5 for the tap water and 3.9 for the Gondegaon well water sample. The minimum tolerance range is 4.0 to 6.0 mg/L for drinking water.

Alkalinity: In the present study, alkalinity is 525 mg/L for tap water and 500 mg/L for Gondegaon well water sample. The tolerance of alkalinity is 200 mg/L for drinking water.

Turbidity: In the present study, turbidity is 5NTU for both tap water and Gondegaon well water sample. According to standards, the minimum tolerance range is 5NTU.

Hardness: In the present study, hardness is 570 mg/L for tap water and 375 mg/L for Gondegaon well water sample. According to WHO and Indian Standards, hardness value should be 300 mg/L for drinking water.

B.O.D: In the present study, the BOD is 3.5 for tap water and 3.2 for Gondegaon well water sample. The minimum tolerance range is 3.0 mg/L for drinking water.

Fluorides: In the present study, fluorides content is 1.0 mg/L for tap water and 0.5 mg/L for Gondegaon well water sample. The minimum tolerance range of fluorides is 1.0 to 1.5 mg/L for drinking water.

Chlorides: In the present study, pH ranged from 420 mg/L for tap water and 300 mg/L for Ghonde Gaon well water sample. The tolerance chlorides content is 200 to 1000 mg/L.

Nitrates: In the present study, nitrates content is 45 mg/L for tap water and 10 mg/L for Ghonde Gaon well water sample. According to Indian Standards, nitrates value should be ranged from 20 to 45 mg/L for drinking water.

Iron: In the present study, iron content is 0.1 mg/L for tap water and 0.3 mg/L for Ghonde Gaon well water sample. The minimum tolerance range is 0.3 mg/L for drinking water.

Table 2: Experimentally Calculated values for Pre Monsoon of Water Quality Parameters

Sr. no.	Characteristics	Experimentally calculated values	
		Tap water	Ghonde Gaon well water
1.	pH	5.6	5.9
2.	Temperature	25	25
3.	Alkalinity	425	390
4.	Hardness (mg/L)	380	255
5.	Turbidity (NTU)	4	4
6.	Total dissolved solids	800	700
7.	BOD	2.8	1.9
8.	DO (mg/L) (max.)	3.5	2.5
9.	Fluorides (mg/L) (max.)	0.75	0.35
10.	Chlorides (mg/L) (max.)	210	150
11.	Nitrates (mg/L) (max.)	25	5
12.	Iron (mg/L) (max.)	0.05	0.1

The following parameters calculated from the experimental work are of pre monsoon May – 2014 of Sukena village are explained as follows:-

Temperature: In the present study, the temperature is 25°C.

pH: In the present study, pH is 5.6 for tap water and 5.9 for Gondegaon well water sample. The tolerance pH limit is 6.5 – 8.5.

TDS: In the present study, total dissolved solids value is 800 for the tap water and 700 for the Gondegaon well water sample. According to Indian Standards, TDS value should be less than 500 mg/L for drinking water.

D.O.: In the present study, the dissolved oxygen is 3.5 for the tap water and 2.5 for the Gondegaon well water sample. The minimum tolerance range is 4.0 to 6.0 mg/L for drinking water.

Alkalinity: In the present study, alkalinity is 425 mg/L for tap water and 390 mg/L for Gondegaon well water sample. The tolerance of alkalinity is 200 mg/L for drinking water.

Turbidity: In the present study, turbidity is 4 NTU for both tap water and Gondegaon well water sample. According to standards, the minimum tolerance range is 5NTU.

Hardness: In the present study, hardness is 380 mg/L for tap water and 255 mg/L for Gondegaon well water sample. According to WHO and Indian Standards, hardness value should be 300 mg/L for drinking water.

B.O.D: In the present study, the BOD is 2.8 for tap water and 1.9 for Gondegaon well water sample. The minimum tolerance range is 3.0 mg/L for drinking water.

Figure 3: Graph Analysis on the Pre monsoon (May 2014) Water Quality Parameters

Fluorides: In the present study, fluorides content is 0.75 mg/L for tap water and 0.35 mg/L for Gondegaoon well water sample. The minimum tolerance range of fluorides is 1.0 to 1.5 mg/L for drinking water.

Chlorides: In the present study, chlorides ranged from 210 mg/L for tap water and 150 mg/L for Gondegaoon well water sample. The tolerance chlorides content is 200 to 1000 mg/L.

Nitrates: In the present study, nitrates content is 25 mg/L for tap water and 5 mg/L for Gondegaoon well water sample. According to Indian Standards, nitrates value should be ranged from 20 to 45 mg/L for drinking water.

Iron: In the present study, iron content is 0.05 mg/L for tap water and 0.1 mg/L for Gondegaoon well water sample. The minimum tolerance range is 0.3 mg/L for drinking water.

Table 3: Contaminated Soil analysis values from experimental work

Sr. no.	Parameters	Results	Units
1.	pH (1:5 Suspension)	8.31	-
2.	Bulk Density	0.83	g/cm ³
3.	Porosity	31.5	%
4.	Water Holding Capacity	74.8	%
5.	Organic Carbon	2.36	%
6.	Total Nitrogen (as N)	2697	Kg/ha
7.	Available Phosphorus (as P)	435	Kg/ha
8.	Available Potassium (as K)	6082	Kg/ha
9.	Cation Exchange Capacity	14	Meq/ 100g
10.	Available Boron (as B)	8.40	mg/kg
11.	Nitrite	0.34	mg/kg
12.	Acidity (as CaCO ₃)	0	%

Figure 4: Graph Analysis on the Contaminated Soil Quality Parameters:

The following parameters calculated from the experimental work of contaminated soil of Sukena village are explained as follows:-

pH: In this study, pH content is 8.31. The minimum tolerance range of the pH is 6-8.2. As this is more, it is problematic and typically appears to be nutrients deficiencies. And soil is alkaline and sodic in nature.

Bulk Density: In this study, the bulk density is 0.83. The minimum tolerance value of bulk density is 0.01 to 1.5. The bulk density of soil indicates the degree of compaction of soil and is defined as the mass per unit volume.

Porosity: In this study, the porosity is 31.5 in %.

Water Holding Capacity: In this study, the water holding capacity is 74.8 in %. It is an index of number of physical property of soil. Here the percentage of soil is more than 0.25mm and good water holding capacity of the soil gives good physical condition of soil.

Organic Carbon: In this study, the organic carbon is 2.36 in %. Bulk density decreases with increase in organic carbon. The minimum tolerance range of the organic carbon is 200-400.

Total Nitrogen: In this study, the total nitrogen is 2697 kg/ha. The minimum tolerance of total nitrogen is 281-560 kg/ha. The nitrogen is the most important fertilizer element. The overall increase in nitrogen is due to the use of sewage water, which contains high amount of nitrogen. The sewage water significantly increased the nitrogen in soil.

Available Phosphorus: In this study, the available phosphorus is 435 kg/ha. The minimum tolerance range of available phosphorus is 120-150 kg/ha. Soil irrigated with sewage water contains higher amount of available phosphorous which play significant role in plant growth.

Available Potassium: In this study, the available potassium is 6082 kg/ha. The minimum tolerance of the available potassium is 150-275 kg/ha. Available potassium content of soil increases significantly by the sewage water application.

Cation Exchange Capacity: In this study, the cation exchange capacity is 14 Meq/100g. The minimum tolerance value of cation exchange capacity should be less than 1 and more than 100 cmol/kg.

Available Boron: In this study, the available boron is 8.40 mg/kg..

Nitrite: In this study, the nitrite value is 0.34 mg/kg.

Table 4: Contaminated Water analysis values from experimental work

Sr. no.	Parameters	Results	Units
1.	pH	7.52	-
2.	Total Solids	1614	Mg/lit
3.	BOD (3 days, 27°C)	180	Mg/lit
4.	COD	536	Mg/lit
5.	Salinity	0.82	%
6.	Calcium (as Ca)	140	Mg/lit
7.	Magnesium (as Mg)	75.3	Mg/lit
8.	Sulphate (as SO ₄)	63.2	Mg/lit
9.	Nitrites (as NO ₂)	< 0.02	Mg/lit
10.	Total Organic Carbon	49	Mg/lit
11.	Surfactants	2.08	Mg/lit
12.	E. coli	220	MPN Index / 100 ml

Figure 5: Graph Analysis on the Contaminated Water Quality Parameters

The following parameters calculated from the experimental work of contaminated water of Sukena village are explained as follows:-

pH: In this study, pH content is 7.52. The minimum tolerance range of the pH is 5.5 – 8.4.

Total Solids: In this study, the total solid is 1614. The minimum tolerance value of

total solids is 500 - 2000.

BOD (3 Days, 27°C): In this study, the BOD value is 180. The minimum tolerance range of the BOD is 133.

COD: In this study, the COD value is 536. The tolerance range of COD is 29-71.

Salinity: In this study, the salinity value is 0.82. The tolerance value of salinity is 0.4 – 0.8.

Calcium: In this study, the calcium is 140. The minimum tolerance of calcium is 75 – 200.

Magnesium: In this study, the magnesium is 75.3. The minimum tolerance range of magnesium is 30 – 100.

Sulphates: In this study, the sulphates value is 63.2. The minimum tolerance value of sulphate is less than 500.

Nitrites: In this study, the nitrites value is 0.02. The tolerance value of nitrite is less than 500.

Total Organic Carbon: In this study, the total organic carbon is 49. The minimum tolerance range value of total organic carbon is 150.

Surfactants: In this study, the surfactants value is 2.08. The minimum tolerance value of the surfactant is 34.

E. coli: In this study, the E. coli value is 220. The minimum tolerance value of E. coli is less than 1000.

In this, the BOD, COD, salinity is more and other parameters are within the permissible limit.

Table 5: Pesticides Concentration Analysis present in the Ghonde Gaon Well and Bhandare's Well (Individual Well of the farmer)

Sr. no.	Pesticides	Calculated Results for Ghonde well water sample	Calculated Results for Bhandare's well water sample	Maximum Contaminant Level Observed Results	Units
1.	Atrazine	<0.05	<0.05	0.003	µg/L
2.	Aldrin	<0.05	<0.05	0.027-0.20	µg/L
3.	Dieldrin	<0.05	<0.05	0.1-0.195	µg/L
4.	2,4 – D	0.1	0.13	0.07	µg/L
5.	p, p DDT	<0.05	<0.05	0.025	µg/L
6.	o, p DDT	<0.05	<0.05	0.085	µg/L
7.	p, p DDE	<0.05	<0.05	0.12	µg/L
8.	o, p DDE	<0.05	<0.05	0.14	µg/L
9.	p, p DDD	<0.05	<0.05	0.090	µg/L
10.	o, p DDD	<0.05	<0.05	0.1	µg/L
11.	α Endosulfan	<0.05	<0.05	0.32	µg/L
12.	β Endosulfan	<0.05	<0.05	0.33	µg/L
13.	γ HCH (Lindane)	<0.05	<0.05	0.0002	µg/L

Figure 6: Graph Analysis on the Ghonde Gaon well and Bhandare's well Water Quality Parameter

The following parameters calculated from the experimental work of water affected by the pesticides of Sukena village are explained as follows:-

Atrazine: In this study, the Atrazine concentration is less than 0.05 µg/L for both the Ghonde Gaon well and Bhandare's well. The maximum permissible limit of Atrazine is 0.003 µg/L.

Aldrin: In this study, the Aldrin concentration is less than 0.05 µg/L for both the Ghonde Gaon well and Bhandare's well. The maximum permissible limit of Aldrin is 0.027 – 0.20 µg/L.

Dieldrin: In this study, the Dieldrin concentration is less than 0.05 µg/L for both the Ghonde Gaon well and Bhandare's well. The maximum permissible limit of Dieldrin is 0.1- 0.195 µg/L.

2, 4 – D: In this study, the 2, 4 – D concentration is less than 0.1 µg/L for Ghonde Gaon well and 0.13 µg/L for Bhandare's well. The maximum permissible limit of 2, 4 – D is 0.07 µg/L.

p, p DDT: In this study, the p, p DDT concentration is less than 0.05 µg/L for both the Ghonde Gaon well and Bhandare's well. The maximum permissible limit of p, p DDT is 0.025 µg/L.

o, p DDT: In this study, the o, p DDT concentration is less than 0.05 µg/L for both the Ghonde Gaon well and Bhandare's well. The maximum permissible limit of o, p DDT is 0.085µg/L.

p, p DDE: In this study, the p, p DDE concentration is less than 0.05 µg/L for both the Ghonde Gaon well and Bhandare's well. The maximum permissible limit of p, p DDE is 0.12 µg/L.

o, p DDE: In this study, the o, p DDE concentration is less than 0.05 µg/L for both the Ghonde Gaon well and Bhandare's well. The maximum permissible limit of o, p DDE is 0.14 µg/L.

p, p DDD: In this study, the p, p DDD concentration is less than 0.05 µg/L for both the Ghonde Gaon well and Bhandare's well. The maximum permissible limit of p, p DDD is 0.090 µg/L.

o, p DDD: In this study, the o, p DDD concentration is less than 0.05 µg/L for both the Ghonde Gaon well and Bhandare's well. The maximum permissible limit of o, p DDD is 0.1 µg/L.

α Endosulfan: In this study, the α Endosulfan concentration is less than 0.05 µg/L for both the Ghonde Gaon well and Bhandare's well. The maximum permissible limit of α Endosulfan is 0.33 µg/L.

β Endosulfan: In this study, the β Endosulfan concentration is less than 0.05 µg/L for both the Ghonde Gaon well and Bhandare's well. The maximum permissible limit of β Endosulfan is 0.34 µg/L.

γ HCH (Lindane): In this study, the γ HCH (Lindane) concentration is less than 0.05 µg/L for both the Ghonde Gaon well and Bhandare's well. The maximum permissible limit of γ HCH (Lindane) is 0.0002 µg/L.

IV. CONCLUSION

1. By posting the banners and conducting the campaigns in the Sukena village, awareness about the utilization of water and the cleaning, maintaining of the toilets in a proper way.
2. The water directly supplied from the Godavari River to the main water tank in the Sukena village, is not pure. So the doctor usually preferred for the TCL powder for the filtering purpose and give suggestion to the villagers to boil the water before using, as there is no other facility of filtering the water or any treatment plant.
3. The proper disposal of solid, liquid and greywater should be done so that there should not be any blockage of drainage pipeline/chamber and the provision of water to the villagers should not be polluted due to this.
4. The drainage chambers should be constructed properly in the closed loop, so that the house flies and breeding of mosquitoes will be reduced and the increase in the water borne diseases will be minimized.
5. The Ghanta gadi (vehicle), for the storage of solid waste i.e. dry and wet solid wastes should be allotted in each lane so as to minimize the direct disposal in open areas.
6. The costing is to be calculated for the constructing of the single toilet block for the single family.
7. The testing is to be done over the drinking water, contaminated soil and contaminated water and the water collected from the wells for the checking of pesticides concentration with the help of linear regression. And the final results are the water should be purified in proper way and then come in the utilization of domestic purpose; the contaminated soil is feasible for the gardening as the percentage of total nitrogen, available phosphorus and available potassium is more, it is good for the soil fertility; the contaminated water is not feasible for the gardening purpose, only for the flushing of toilet blocks and the water from the wells are not contaminated due to pesticides as the pesticides concentration is very less than the permissible limit.

8. The water pipelines level should be allotted above the drainage pipelines level, so that neither the leakage of the pipelines will be occurred nor the mixing of the waste water will be done with the supply of the drinking water to the Sukena village.

9. Awareness should be increased by proper hand-washing should be done after utility of sanitary block and before taking the meal, the sanitary blocks should be properly cleaned up after use i.e. proper utilization of water after use of sanitary block respectively.

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